

A golden-gate compatible TRV2 virus induced gene silencing (VIGS) vector.

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Abstract and Introduction

Virus induced gene silencing (VIGS) is a useful tool in plant biology to systemically silence a gene by RNA interference (RNAi). Co-expression of tobacco rattle virus 1 (TRV1), which contains the genome of the viral vector, with TRV2 containing the target sequence for RNAi, can be achieved by *Agrobacterium*-mediated gene expression in *Nicotiana benthamiana* (Burch-Smith et al., 2006). Existing methods of cloning TRV2 plasmids with the targeting sequence of interest include time consuming Restriction-Ligation cloning, expensive Gateway cloning or Ligation Independent Cloning (LIC). Whilst LIC is relatively quick and cost-effective, it relies on having a pre-linearised vector. Therefore, Golden-Gate cloning is preferable in that it is a 1-step cloning method. Therefore, we modified the existing TRV2 vector to be compatible with golden gate cloning. To add extra flexibility, we incorporated the overhangs used for pRNAiGG, a vector for carrying out transient, local silencing in leaf tissue by hairpin RNAi (Yan et al., 2012). Therefore, the resulting TRV2gg is compatible with the same insert for pRNAiGG enabling transient, local silencing or systemic silencing. TRV2gg contains an unwanted BsaI recognition site in the backbone, however a simple golden gate protocol of 37°C for 2 h or a protocol that ends with a ligation-optimised step, is sufficient to easily clone multiple positive colonies.

TRV2gg will be available through addgene, please wait for an updated version of this preprint which will have the link for addgene embedded here.

pRNAiGG

High-Throughput Construction of Intron-Containing Hairpin RNA Vectors for RNAi in Plants
Yan P, Shen W, Gao X, Li X, Zhou P, et al. (2012) High-Throughput Construction of Intron-Containing Hairpin RNA Vectors for RNAi in Plants. PLOS ONE 7(5): e38186.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0038186>

Order: <https://abrc.osu.edu/stocks/number/CD3-1786>

TRV1 and TRV2-GATEWAY

Tessa M. Burch-Smith, Michael Schiff, Yule Liu, S.P. Dinesh-Kumar, Efficient Virus-Induced Gene Silencing in Arabidopsis, Plant Physiology, Volume 142, Issue 1, September 2006, Pages 21–27, <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.106.084624>

Order TRV1: <https://abrc.osu.edu/stocks/number/CD3-1039>

Order TRV2-GATEWAY: <https://abrc.osu.edu/stocks/number/CD3-1041>

Protocol:

Primer design

Forward: 5'- acca ggtctc aggag - gene specific forward primer-3'

Reverse: 5'- acca ggtctc atcgt- gene specific reverse primer-3'

Vector preparation

The vector is supplied in DB3.1 ccdB survival *E. coli* cells. Grow a liquid culture overnight, make a glycerol stock for your -80°C long term storage, and miniprep the rest to release plasmids.

Insert preparation

PCR amplify your insert with primers designed with the sequences below. Alternatively order a double stranded DNA fragment by gene synthesis and include the overhangs as follows:

5' - acca ggtctc aggag - DNA fragment sequence - acgat gagacc tggt -3'

Golden-gate assembly

1. Mix the following in a PCR tube:

Vector	100ng TRV2gg
Insert (PCR purified or synthetic fragment)	2:1 molar ratio of insert:vector
Ligase buffer (10x)	1 µl
T4 DNA ligase	0.5-1µl (10-20U)
Bsal	0.5-1µl (5-10U)
Nuclease free water	Up to 10 µl

2. Incubate at 37°C for 2h, 5 min 80°C

- DO NOT ADD 50°C DIGESTION AT END (due to Bsal cutting site in backbone)
- Tip: If you have issues cloning you can add 10U fresh ligase to the mix after the heat inactivation for a second ligation for 1h at 16°C.

Transformation

Transform 2-10 µl to DH5a (ccdB susceptible cells) or straight to *Agrobacterium* (not recommended as sequencing is harder). Plate 50-200 µl of the cells on LB agar supplemented with 25 µg/ml Kanamycin and grow overnight at 37°C.

Screening

Almost all colonies should be positive, but they can be screened based on insert size with colony PCR using the primer pair in the primer table, suggested Ta = 58°C. The same primers can be used for sequencing.

How TRV2gg was cloned:

Initially we attempted to linearise TRV2 by restriction enzyme digestion and clone the golden gate compatible *ccdB* module into it via gibbon assembly. However, after several failed attempts we decided to perform inverse or circular PCR with short primers facing away from one another removing the gateway *att* sequences and using high-fidelity Phusion polymerase to amplify the rest of the vector. This strategy worked well and we used gibbon assembly to insert the golden gate compatible *ccdB* module, resulting in a circular vector (TRV2gg) that can be cut with *Bsa*I to remove the *ccdB* module and insert fragments compatible with TRV2gg/pRNAiGG.

Figure 1: Generation of pTRV2gg vector for compatibility with PCR fragments produced for pRNAiGG vector. pTRV2-GATEWAY (YL279) vector was linearised (PCR fragment 1) and gateway ‘att’ sites removed by high fidelity (HF) PCR with primers 1 & 2 (Ta = 70°C; extension time = 2 min 45 s), and the *ccdB* and golden-gate compatibility sites were amplified (PCR fragment 2) by primers 3 & 4 (Ta = 60°C; extension = 30s; pRNAiGG template), containing overhangs to fragment 1 for Gibson Assembly that circularised the plasmid. This was grown in *ccdB*-resistant cells (db3.1 competent *E. coli*) and minipreped for golden-gate and transformation into *ccdB*-susceptible DH5-alpha competent *E. coli*.

Verification of silencing

Next to show if we cloned a fragment targeting GFP or MPK3 and 6 into TRV2gg. For this we took a PCR-amplified fragment for GFP (primers listed below) and a fragment targeting both MAPK3 and 6 and carried out a golden gate assembly.

To verify whether the constructs were silencing we took leaf disks from 4-week silenced plants and carried out RT-PCR for RNA extracted from MPK3/6 plants (Figure 2). We found that the MPK3/6 silencing resulted in a clear decrease in band intensity corresponding to RNA from MPK3/6 treated plants for both MPK3 and MPK6.

Figure 2: TRV2gg-MPK3/6 silences *NbMPK6* and *NbMPK3*. *N. benthamiana* plants 4-weeks post treatment with TRV2gg-MPK3/6 or TRV2-EV were chosen and leaf disks frozen. RNA was extracted and cDNA produced. The resulting cDNA was used as templates for PCRs with primers amplifying *NbMPK3*, *NbMPK6* or *NbGAPDH*. TRV2gg-MPK3/6 silenced *NbMPK3*, and *NbMPK6* but not the loading control *NbGAPDH*.

Next we confirmed that TRV2gg:GFP treatment reduces the GFP protein levels (Figure 3). We carried out VIGS on SP-GFP-HDEL (ER-GFP marker) *N. benthamiana* transgenic lines. After 4 weeks we crushed leaf disks from these and TRV2:EV treated plants, crudely extracted proteins, separated them by SDS-PAGE and conducted western blotting for GFP. We found no GFP signal in the silenced lane, but a clear band corresponding to GFP (as well as a degradation product below it).

Figure 3: TRV2gg:GFP silences GFP protein expression. Proteins from untreated Wild type *N. benthamiana* or SP-GFP-HDEL transgenics treated with TRV2gg:GFP or TRV2:EV were separated on a 12% gel TRIS-Glycine SDS-PAGE gel, before being transferred to a PVDF membrane and probed by a monoclonal anti-GFP antibody. Signal corresponding to GFP was only seen in the EV treated lane.

Discussion

TRV2gg represents a useful tool for efficiently cloning TRV2 constructs targeting genes of interest, but also the flexibility of its compatibility with pRNAiGG means that the same double stranded DNA fragments targeting your gene of interest can be inserted into either vector (Yan et al., 2012). This allows you to transiently silence a local region on a leaf with pRNAiGG or systemically silence the whole plant with TRV2gg. These synergistic tools will help plant scientists speed up functional validation of their genes of interest.

Methods

Cloning

High-fidelity PCR was conducted with the primers, template, annealing temperature and extension time indicated in Figure 1. Primer sequences can be found in the table below. Phusion polymerase (pPCR). 50µl reactions were made up of 10 µl HF buffer (10x) [ThermoFisher], 1 µl Forward primer (100 pmol/µl), 1µl Reverse primer (100pmol/ul), 1 µl template DNA (1ng/µl plasmid), 0.5 µl Phusion polymerase (2U/µl) [ThermoFisher], 1 µl dNTPs (40mM) [Promega]. 10 µl PCR products were mixed with 2 µl of TriTrack DNA loading dye (6x) [ThermoFisher]. This was loaded into 1% Agarose gels made with 1x TBE and 0.5 µl SyberSafe stain per 40 ml gel. Electrophoresis was carried out in 1x TBE at 100V for 40 m. Gels were imaged using a Syngene blue light transilluminator. Those PCR products that were correctly amplified were purified with Promega PCR purification kits. Next Gibson assembly was carried out with 5 µl home-made Gibson assembly mix (2µL of 5x ISO Buffer, 4nL 10U/µL T5 exonuclease [NEB], 0.1µL of 2 U/µL Phusion polymerase

[ThermoFisher], 0.6 µL of 40U/µL Taq DNA ligase [NEB] and 0.6µL of nuclease free water)), 50 ng linearised vector was added to 5 ng ccdB insert to achieve a 2:1 molar ratio of insert(s) to vector. 5x isothermal (ISO) buffer is 3mL of 1M Tris-HCl pH 7.5 150 µl, 2M MgCl₂, 240µL of 100mM dNTPs, 300 µl of 1M DTT, 1.5g PEG-8000, 300 µl of 100mM NAD – nuclease free water to 6mL. The reaction was topped up to 10 µl with nuclease free water and incubated at 50 °C for 1 h. This was transformed into db3.1 chemically competent ccdB resistant *E. coli* cells (contains ccdA).

Virus Induced Gene Silencing

Agrobacterium cultures carrying Tobacco Rattle Virus (TRV) 1 (OD₆₀₀ = 0.4) and gene specific TRV2 (OD₆₀₀ = 0.2) were prepared as before, but *agroinfiltration* buffer with 100 µM acetosyringone and cultures were left in the dark for 2 h prior to infiltration, to stimulate virulence. Seedlings approximately 10 days old were infiltrated. Both cotyledons and any true leaves that had emerged were infiltrated. Plants were left to grow under normal conditions until experiments could be performed 4 weeks later.

Primer sequence table

Primer 1	CTCCCGGTAACCTTACTCACAGAATCT
Primer 2	ACGAGGTACCGAGCTCACGCGTCT
Primer 3	TTCTGTGAGTAAGGTTACCGGGAGTGAGACCAATTCTCGACTA A
Primer 4	AGACGCGTGAGCTCGGTACCTCGTTGAGACCGTCGACCTGT
TRV2gg:GFP_F	ACCAGGTCTCAGGAGGACGTAAACGGCCAC
TRV2gg:GFP_R	ACCAGGTCTCATCGTCTTCTGCTTGTGCGGC
TRV2gg colony PCR F	ACTCAAGGAAGCACGATG
TRV2gg colony PCR R	TAATGTCTTCGGGACATGC
RT_NbMPK3_Fr	TCATGTATCAGCTCCTCCGTG
RT_NbMPK3_Rv	CGAGGATGTTGTGGGAGTTG
RT_NbMPK6_Fr	ATGGATGGTTCTGGTCAGCA
RT_NbMPK6_Rv	AAGGCTTCTCTCTGTGGTGG
RNAiGG_MPK3_Fr	ACCAGGTCTCAGGAGATCACTACCAAGTATCGTCTCCTCC
RNAiGG_MPK3_Rv	ACCAGGTCTCATCGTCCTCTGATAAACCTTGGTTGGATC
RNAiGG_MPK6_Fr	ACCAGGTCTCAGGAGCCTGGTAGAGATCACGTACACC
RNAiGG_MPK6_Rv	ACCAGGTCTCATCGTGGATTAAATGCAAGCGACTCCC